

A Semi-Implicit Poisson Box Sampling Method for Dispersion Fuel Analysis in RMC Code - Preliminary Investigations

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ABSTRACT

The modelling of particle transport through stochastic geometry such as dispersion fuel is a fundamental part of nuclear reactor simulations. The Poisson Box Sampling (PBS) methods are a new family of algorithms aimed at accurately modelling particle transport through binary Markov mixtures through approximating ensemble-averaged observables for particle transport. Due to the partial memoryless nature of the method, where previously generated boxes are discarded as new boxes are sampled, PBS partially neglects memory effects and spatial correlations between boxes, ultimately resulting in discrepancies with reference solutions. In this work, we explore methods to account for memory effects in PBS for dispersion fuel analysis, using ensemble-averaged results from quenched-disorder modelling methods as benchmark solutions. We propose the Semi-Implicit Poisson Box Sampling (SIPBS) method, using an Dynamic Inclusion Sphere to retain only boxes within a certain range of the particle's position, with the goal of accounting for the most relevant spatial correlations whilst retaining computational efficiency. The results show that SIPBS is able to produce results that are significantly closer to the benchmark results compared to PBS, being able to reproduce results with higher accuracy at a reasonable increase in computational expense.

Keywords: Memory Effects, Stochastic Media, Dispersion Fuel, Poisson Box Sampling, Reactor Monte Carlo

1. INTRODUCTION

Stochastic geometry are present in nuclear reactors in various forms; as stochastic and dynamically turbulent molten fuel in Molten-Salt Reactors (MSRs) [1], randomly arranged fuel pebble distributions or micro-fuel particulate in dispersion fuel in High Temperature Gas-Cooled Reactors (HTGRs) [2], or non-homogeneous radiation shields in most nuclear reactor systems [3]. As such, the modelling of stochastic geometry is of particular significance in the precise simulation of particle transport codes. In the context of dispersion fuels, these modelling methods can generally be classified into explicit methods (or quenched-disorder models) where a fixed particle distribution is used for neutron transport, or implicit methods (or annealed-disorder models) where particles or inclusions are generated on-the-fly, such as with the Chord Length Sampling (CLS) method.

The basis of PBS lies in the observation by Larmier et al [4] that the physical observables related to particle transport in the quasi-isotropic Poisson tessellations (based on Cartesian boxes) is nearly identical to those calculated in isotropic Poisson tessellations [5]; as such, it has been shown that as long as the material characteristics are provided, PBS variants can be used to approximate particle transport in heterogeneous, randomly shaped stochastic media [4]. PBS has been shown to reproduce results that are consistent and accurate against benchmark problems proposed by Adams, Larsen and Pomraning [6],

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and the algorithm is structured in a manner to accommodate for short-term spatial correlations, through the sampling of a new box that partially retains the box lengths of the previous box, and the retention of the penultimately generated box in memory in PBS-2 [4]. However, due to the partial memoryless nature of PBS, previously generated boxes are eventually eliminated from memory, and as such PBS is unable to completely consider all spatial correlations and memory effects induced during the particle's transport.

Hence, in this paper, we explore methods to account for memory effects in PBS for dispersion fuel analysis, thus improving its accuracy against explicit modelling methods. This paper will be organized into the following sections. In Section 2, we briefly describe the methodology of the PBS method, as well as introduce the Semi-Implicit Poisson Box Sampling (SIPBS) method here, where we limit the number of boxes (generated on-the-fly) retained in memory to a range around the particle's position. This SIPBS method is integrated into Reactor Monte Carlo (RMC) code, a continuous-energy Reactor Monte Carlo neutron and photon transport code currently being developed by the Department of Engineering Physics at Tsinghua University, Beijing [7]. We thus examine the accuracy and effectiveness of SIPBS against that of PBS, CLS and the explicit Random Sequential Addition (RSA) [8] in Section 3, to understand the viability and effectiveness of said methods. Section 4 discusses the limitations of the research presented in this paper, as well as future work. Section 5 thus summarizes the findings and concludes the paper.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Algorithmic Flow for PBS

For the purposes of this paper, we will primarily discuss PBS in the context of neutron transport through dispersion fuel. The average chord length for spherical particles suspended in a matrix can be derived from Torquato et al [9].

- Step 0: With the given average chord length $(\Lambda_\alpha, \Lambda_\beta)$ for each material (α, β) in the binary stochastic medium, derive the correlation length of the geometry via $\Lambda = (1 - p_\alpha)\Lambda_\alpha$ or $\Lambda = p_\alpha\Lambda_\beta$, where p_α and p_β are the material fractions of α and β respectively.
- Step 1: Initialize each particle from its source, along with its specified initial positional coordinates and angles. Generate a random Cartesian box around the particle. The box is defined by the material label i (sampled from the given overall material composition) and its spatial position, given by the center coordinates of the box (x_c, y_c, z_c) , and its side lengths (l_x, l_y, l_z) . For the primary box, three pairs of random numbers (Δ_x^+, Δ_x^-) , (Δ_y^+, Δ_y^-) and (Δ_z^+, Δ_z^-) are sampled from independent exponential distributions of average $3\Lambda/2$. The center and side lengths of the box are thus defined as:

$$x_c = x + (\Delta_x^+ - \Delta_x^-)/2; y_c = y + (\Delta_y^+ - \Delta_y^-)/2; z_c = z + (\Delta_z^+ - \Delta_z^-)/2 \quad (1)$$

$$l_x = \Delta_x^+ + \Delta_x^-; l_y = \Delta_y^+ + \Delta_y^-; l_z = \Delta_z^+ + \Delta_z^- \quad (2)$$

- Step 2: Three distances are computed using the current particle position and directions: the distance to next physical boundary l_b ; the distance to collision l_c (determined by the macroscopic cross section Σ_i of the selected box material i from Step 1, where l_c is drawn from an exponential distribution with an average of $1/\Sigma_i$); and the distance to box interface l_i , calculated with the given positions of the box surfaces.
- Step 3: The minimum distance amongst l_b , l_c , and l_i is selected, and the particle accordingly moves this selected distance along its current direction. If the minimum is l_b , the particle hits the physical boundary, and the direction of the particle will then be updated upon the imposition of any reflective properties of this boundary. If the minimum is l_c , the particle undergoes a collision event at its new position, and material properties are selected as per the material label i of the box. If the

minimum is l_i , the particle intersects the surface of the current box – a new box is generated as per Step 4, and the new box then becomes the current box. If the particle survives without capture, the algorithm returns to Step 2.

- Step 4: A new random spacing Δ_{new} is first drawn from an exponential distribution with average $3\Lambda/2$. The intersected surface determines which surface of the box are retained and which are discarded or replaced. For instance, if the intersected surface of the box is perpendicular to the x-axis, a new box is thus generated, with the length of this new box along the x-axis $l_x = \Delta_{new}$, whilst retaining the other box parameters $l_y, l_z, y_c,$ and z_c . x_c is then updated, with $x_c = x_{particle} + l_x \cdot w_x / \|w_x\|$ where w_x represents the particle direction along the x-axis. Effectively, if the particle collides with the upper x-surface of the box, the upper x-surface is thus treated as the lower x-surface of the new box, and the upper x-surface of the new box is treated as $\Delta_z^+ + l_x$.

The PBS-1 method thus consists of iterating between Steps 2-4 until the particle has either been absorbed or has escaped the medium. In the PBS-2 variant, the penultimate box is retained in memory, and if the particle is transported to the interface where the current box meets the previous box, the previous box will then become the current box and vice versa, with the material and spatial parameters of the previous box being utilized again for the remainder of the particle’s transport process within the re-generated box. In this set of experiments, we utilize only PBS-1 for our comparison.

2.2. Semi-Implicit Poisson Box Sampling

The SIPBS method consists of two main modifications to PBS; namely, a Dynamic Inclusion Sphere method as described in Section 2.2.1, and additional algorithmic considerations regarding how the method handles overlapping boxes, as described in Section 2.2.2.

2.2.1. The Dynamic Inclusion Sphere Method

The recording of previous histories as elaborated in Larmier et al’s PBS-2 variant [4] has been shown to improve the accuracy of the reproduced results. However, the feasibility of increasing the number of boxes retained in memory indefinitely is called into question when simulating large and complex geometries, where the retention of histories may result in high computational expenses. Hence, we introduce the Dynamic Inclusion Sphere method to retain the most relevant box histories.

Step n :

Neutron travels from B to C. The Dynamic Inclusion Sphere is thus centred at C, and the histories of the boxes that are partially or fully located within the sphere are retained.

Step $n + 1$:

Neutron travels from C to D, and then encounters a collision, where it subsequently travels to E. The position of the Dynamic Inclusion Sphere is thus updated, and the histories of any boxes located fully outside the sphere are removed from memory.

Figure 1. The Dynamic Inclusion Sphere Method.

The dynamic inclusion sphere is a sphere centered on the neutron itself. As shown in Fig 1, the sphere

is generated around the neutron, and its position is updated when the neutron is transported through the stochastic media. When the neutron travels from C to E, it can be seen that the previously generated box in the top left corner is removed from memory. Using this method, the most relevant histories can be defined as the histories that are located in the vicinity of the neutron itself.

As the neutron travels from the moment of birth to its end, the inclusion sphere must be sufficiently large to capture the relevant box histories, but not too large as to diminish the computational efficiency of the algorithm. The radius must also be defined in such a way that the method is able to provide consistent results for different particle sizes and materials. Hence, we have defined the radius as the transport mean free path (TMFP) through the entire stochastic media. The TMFP [10] is defined as:

$$\lambda_{TMFP} = \frac{1}{\Sigma_s(1 - \bar{\mu})} \quad (3)$$

where for a dispersion fuel, the values of the macroscopic scattering cross section Σ_s and the average value of the cosine of the angle at which neutrons are scattered $\bar{\mu}$ are derived overall from the dispersion fuel material, with consideration to the energy of the particle. The TMFP represents the average distance a neutron travels in its initial direction after undergoing an infinite number of scattering collisions, and is a suitable indicator of the average distance the neutron will travel before being absorbed. By retaining only the most useful and relevant histories to reduce the computational expense of the method, we aim to generalize the method for different modeling conditions.

Figure 2. Two different methods of handling overlap in SIPBS.

2.2.2. Algorithmic Handling of Box Overlap

With the retention of multiple boxes in memory, a scenario occurs as shown in Fig 2, where newly sampled boxes may overlap with their previously generated counterparts. Here, we examine two different methods of handling overlap, as well as how these methods may potentially introduce inaccuracies in the final results.

The first way of handling overlap, as labelled in Fig 2 as Step $n+1$ (Overlap), is by removing previously generated boxes, and retaining the original size of the newly sampled box. In the example provided by Fig 2, Box A is removed from memory, whilst Box F is retained without modification. However, this method actively neglects spatial correlations; a particle may find itself in the area where Box A and F overlapped, where the area was previously filled with material of Box A, and now by material of Box F. The second way of handling overlap, as shown in Step $n+1$ (No Overlap), involves resizing the length of Box F, until the surface of the newly generated box is flushed to the nearest surface of the nearest amongst the previously generated boxes, resulting in zero overlap between current and previous boxes. While this method considers spatial effects, the process of resizing newly sampled boxes alters the overall mean chord length of the boxes, potentially resulting in a different geometry altogether and ultimately resulting in altered particle transport characteristics. We thus define the SIPBS variant “with overlap” as SIPBS-1, and the SIPBS variant “without overlap” as SIPBS-2.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The algorithm, as a function of RMC code, was run on a AMD Ryzen Threadripper 3990X 64-Core Processor, with only a single thread being used for all computations. For each set of calculations, 100 runs are taken, and the ensemble-averaged results of these 100 runs are compared. For all the tests discussed in this Section, a simplified cuboidal dispersion fuel model was set up, and the model was simulated under RMC’s critical calculation module. Table I illustrates the parameters describing the cuboidal dispersion fuel model, as well as experimental variables such as the number of neutrons and the number of inactive/active cycles. This particular neutron population and cycle number was chosen to maximise the efficiency of the algorithm whilst ensuring that the relative error for the k_{inf} values was maintained within 250 pcm for each run prior to calculating the ensemble-average.

Table I. Experimental Parameters

Parameter	Value
Length/Height/Width	20.0 cm
Particle Packing Fraction	35%
Particle radius	0.4-0.6 cm
Particle material	UO ₂
Matrix material	Graphite
Number of neutrons	100000
Inactive/Active Cycles	100/100
Boundary Condition	Full Reflection

The particle packing fraction was maintained at 35%, while the particle radius was varied between 0.4-0.6 cm. This range was selected to minimize the effect of spatial constraints on the boundaries of the stochastic media, whilst ensuring that the impact of particle radius on computational time could be observed. Fig. 3 and 4 describes the comparison between the k_{inf} against particle radius, and computational time against particle radius respectively. In this experiment, RSA is used as the benchmark due to its highly accurate nature, as particles are explicitly generated without any loss in fidelity; RSA primarily consists of placing particles without overlap in a stochastic medium until the desired packing fraction is achieved.

We can observe that as compared to CLS, both SIPBS variants appear to produce k_{inf} values that become closer to those produced by RSA, for all particle radii tested. The largest and smallest differences be-

Figure 3. k_{inf} Against Particle Radius.

tween the k_{inf} values produced by RSA and CLS are 1570.8 and 855.5 pcm respectively; whereas for RSA and SIPBS-1, the largest and smallest differences are 296.2 and 42.7 pcm respectively, and for RSA and SIPBS-2, the largest and smallest differences are 283.2 and 50.8 pcm respectively. However, SIPBS-1 and SIPBS-2 do not appear to consistently show higher levels of accuracy than PBS across all particle radii. As observed in Fig 3, between the particle radii of 0.40-0.46 cm, the k_{inf} values produced by PBS are numerically closer to RSA than that of SIPBS; however, beyond 0.46 cm, SIPBS-1 and SIPBS-2 appears to reproduce k_{inf} with higher accuracy. Nevertheless, across the full range of particle radii, SIPBS-1 and SIPBS-2 show more consistency compared to PBS; the largest and smallest differences between the k_{inf} values produced by RSA and PBS are 713.2 and 104.9 pcm respectively.

Lastly, as stated in Section 2.2.2, SIPBS-1 suffers from a deliberate neglect of spatial overlap, whilst SIPBS-2 potentially results in a modified mean chord length. Despite the innate inaccuracies of SIPBS, we observe that the k_{inf} values produced by the SIPBS variants are consistently similar with each other. Between each other, the SIPBS variants show a maximum of 24.4 pcm in k_{inf} difference.

With regards to the computational time, it must be noted that the computational time observed here refers to the overall computational time, including inactive/active cycles and other related computations. While RSA generates a static particle distribution at the start of the calculation process, CLS, PBS and SIPBS generate stochastic media on-the-fly. By taking the overall computational time, we also account for the algorithmic differences between handling explicitly and implicitly generated stochastic inclusions. It can be seen that the computational time for RSA is considerably higher than that of CLS, PBS and SIPBS by a huge margin. This can mainly be attributed to the needs of the explicit modelling method, as particle placement using RSA considers particle overlap with both other particles and the boundaries of the stochastic media, as well as the physical particle saturation limits of the fuel configuration. Hence, as particle radius decreases and the overall number of particles increases, the time required to generate dispersion fuel using RSA increases exponentially. On the other hand, CLS, PBS and the SIPBS variants display much shorter computational times, and between PBS and SIPBS, the

Figure 4. Computational Time Against Particle Radius.

computational expense incurred by SIPBS is reasonable compared to the computational expense of the explicit modelling method.

4. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

As illustrated in Section 3, while SIPBS does provide substantial improvements in terms of accuracy over PBS for a limited range of particle radii, we observe that SIPBS cannot fully bridge the gap between implicit and explicit. This is an inherent mechanism in implicit modeling methods and can be considered for future work.

In addition, the results are limited to varying particle radii within the selected range; SIPBS remains unverified for large, complex systems, and its effectiveness across different packing fractions and materials (such as those of high scattering and/or absorbing properties) is also undetermined. In future work, we intend to determine the effectiveness of SIPBS under the extended range of modelling conditions.

Lastly, while we have defined the radius of the Dynamic Inclusion Sphere as the TMFP, this definition is limited and inherently contains inaccuracies due to its approximate nature. As the TMFP represents the average distance a particle travels before its next collision, it does not account for the anisotropy of neutron scattering, nor does it account for multi-group neutron transport. Thus, it may be necessary to explore other methods to define the most "relevant" boxes near the particle. More work can be done to examine other possible definitions of the radius, such as using more rigorous methods for defining diffusion coefficients and transport cross-sections such as the Cumulative Migration Method [11].

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we propose a Semi-Implicit Poisson Box Sampling method to simulate neutron transport through dispersion fuel. To improve the accuracy of PBS, we have retained the history of previously

generated boxes via a Dynamic Inclusion Sphere method, and proposed two different methods of handling box overlap within the algorithm. Using SIPBS, we show that the method retains the substantial improvements PBS offers over CLS whilst being computationally efficient compared to RSA. We also observe that SIPBS offers improved accuracy with respect to the explicit modelling method in RMC, under a selected range of particle radii, with this improved accuracy coming at a reasonable increase in computational expense. Lastly, we have identified potential areas of improvement, such as extending the scope of our tests, and with exploring the definition of the radius of the Dynamic Inclusion Sphere.

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